

Studies in the Camphor Series. Part III. Tautomeric Behaviour of Thiocamphor and the Activity of its Sodium Derivative.

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The formation of isonitrosothiocamphor (Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 647) shows that the methylene group adjacent to C:S in thiocamphor is reactive. The isolation of *C*-substituted benzylidene derivatives of thiocamphor as well as *S*-substituted alkyl derivatives shows that thiocamphor forms two sodium derivatives corresponding to its two tautomeric forms (I) and (II) (*cf.* Tautomerism in camphor, Bredt-Savelsberg, Heinemann, Catherinus and Liibel, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1924, *ii*, **107**, 65 ; 1927, **115**, 235).

The electronegative influence of C:S-group is apparently greater than that of C:O-group as expected from dipole moments (C:O= 2.5; C:S=5. *cf.* Sidgwick 'The Covalent Link in Chemistry', p. 153). This is substantiated by the greater tendency of thioketones to form *S*-substituted alkyl derivatives.

The condensation of sodio thiocamphor with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde gives *C*-benzylidene derivatives, since they yield the oximes of the benzylidene derivatives of camphor. As the corresponding *dl*-camphor derivatives and their oximes are mostly unknown, they have also been prepared by the usual method (*cf.* Haller, *Compt. rend.*, 1891, **113**, 24; 1895, **121**, 36; 1909, **148**, 1490; Wootton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **97**, 410). It has been observed that a small quantity of thioborneol is always formed when metallic sodium is used in these reactions instead of sodamide. A similar phenomenon has also been observed in the case of camphor which gives small quantity of borneol when sodium is used for the preparation of sodio camphor (Brühl, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 3373). This is most probably due to the reduction of thiocamphor as well as

camphor by means of nascent hydrogen which is evolved during its replacement by means of sodium.

These benzylidene derivatives of thiocamphor, unlike those of camphor, are highly coloured crystalline substances. Of these benzylidene and *p*-methoxybenzylidene-thiocamphor are violet, the nitrobenzylidene derivative is blue, and *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene derivative is dark red. These products show in a beautiful manner the influence of substituents in the benzene ring on the chromophoric effect of C:S-group in thiocamphor.

The action of alkyl iodides on the sodio derivative of thiocamphor exclusively gives *S*-substituted derivatives. The products are pale green in colour and have got a faint smell resembling that of organic sulphides, but on keeping, the products slowly decompose developing a strong mercaptanic smell. They readily decolourise dilute solutions of bromine and acid permanganate in the cold. When hydrolysed by means of dilute sulphuric acid (10%), they give corresponding mercaptans and camphor, the alkyl mercaptans being identified through their lead salts, and corresponding disulphides obtained by their oxidation with iodine. When treated with organic bases like aniline, nitroaniline or phenylhydrazine, they give alkyl mercaptans.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzylidene-thiocamphor.—Thiocamphor (10 g.) in sodium-dried benzene (100 c.c.) was treated with finely powdered sodamide (2.5 g.) and the mixture was boiled on the water-bath for nearly 1 hour. Benzaldehyde (6.5 g.) was added to the mixture, cooled in ice. After keeping overnight the product was poured into crushed ice, the benzene solution washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and allowed to evaporate. Purple crystals associated with a viscous liquid separated out, the oil was removed on a porous tile and the residue crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 30°-50°) (charcoal). It was obtained as violet plates, m.p. 105°, yield 5 g. It is soluble in common organic solvents giving a violet solution with green fluorescence. (Found: C, 78.89; H, 8.1; S, 12.37. $C_{17}H_{20}S$ requires C, 79.7; H, 7.8; S, 12.5 per cent).

The *Oxime*, prepared with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate, crystallised from alcohol as colourless, hexagonal plates, m.p. 200°. (Found: N, 5.32. $C_{17}H_{21}ON$ requires N, 5.5 per cent).

Benzylidene-dl-camphor Oxime was prepared by heating for 4 hours at 100°, hydroxylamine hydrochloride and benzylidene-*dl*-camphor (m.p. 82.5°), prepared from *dl*-camphor. Haller records m.p. 78°. It crystallised from alcohol as colourless hexagonal plates, m.p. 200°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 5.41. $C_{17}H_{21}ON$ requires N, 5.5 per cent).

p-Methoxybenzylidene-*dl*-thiocamphor, prepared from thiocamphor (10 g.), sodamide (2.4 g.) and anisaldehyde (8.5 g.), crystallised from petroleum ether as purple prismatic needles, m.p. 118°, yield 5.5 g. It is soluble in ether, benzene, alcohol, chloroform etc., giving brown solutions with green fluorescence. [Found: C, 75.55; H, 8.01; OMe, 10.3; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene) 290. $C_{18}H_{22}OS$ requires C, 75.53; H, 7.7; OMe, 10.84 per cent. M. W., 286]. The *oxime* melts at 171°. (Found: N, 5.03. $C_{18}H_{23}O_2N$ requires N, 4.91 per cent).

p-Methoxybenzylidene-*dl*-camphor was prepared from camphor (10 g.), sodamide (2.5 g.) and anisaldehyde (9 g.) and it was crystallised from petroleum ether as colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 101°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 80.2; H, 8.25. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 8.15 per cent). The *oxime* was prepared by the action of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2 g.) on *p*-methoxybenzylidene-camphor (2 g.) in pyridine (10 c.c.), m.p. 171°, yield 1.2 g. (Found: N, 5.02. $C_{18}H_{23}O_2N$ requires N, 4.91 per cent).

p-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-*dl*-thiocamphor was obtained from thiocamphor (10 g.), molecular sodium (1.5 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (9 g.) in benzene (100 c.c.). It crystallised from alcohol or petroleum ether as silky red, prismatic needles, m.p. 91°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: C, 75.86; H, 8.65; N, 4.78; S, 10.65. $C_{19}H_{25}NS$ requires C, 76.25; H, 8.36; N, 4.68; S, 10.7 per cent).

o-Nitrobenzylidene-*dl*-thiocamphor crystallises from petroleum ether as prismatic needles, m.p. 135°. (Found: C, 67.3; H, 6.65; N, 4.85; S, 10.71. $C_{17}H_{19}O_2NS$ requires C, 67.77; H, 6.31; N, 4.65; S, 10.63 per cent). The substance has a deep blue colour in the solid state and gives a bluish violet solution. The *oxime* crystallises from alcohol as prismatic needles, m.p. 199°. (Found: N, 9.55. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.33 per cent).

S-Methylthiocamphor or Methylbornylene Sulphide.—Thiocamphor (10 g.) was converted to the sodium derivative by the action of sodamide (2.5 g.); and methyl iodide (10 g.) was added to the mixture at 0° and left for 12 hours after which it was heated under reflux on

the water-bath for 2 hours. The mixture was cooled and treated with ice-cold water. The benzene solution was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, benzene evaporated and the liquid distilled at $85-88^{\circ}/12$ mm., yield 3 g. (Found : C, 72.3; H, 9.7; S, 17.43. $C_{11}H_{18}S$ requires C, 72.52; H, 9.9; S, 17.58 per cent). The colourless liquid has got the smell characteristic of sulphides but on keeping it slowly decomposes and develops mercaptanic smell.

Hydrolysis of S-Methylthiocamphor.—S-methylthiocamphor (2 g.) and sulphuric acid (10%, 20 c.c.) were heated on a sand-bath at $150-60^{\circ}$. The evolved mercaptan was led through a delivery tube attached to the condenser into lead acetate solution when it formed yellow lead salt crystallisable from alcohol which shrinks at 143° and melts at 165° (decomp.). The mercaptan has also been identified as dimethyl disulphide formed by passing the product into an alcoholic solution of iodine. The solution is diluted with water, extracted with ether, dried over sodium sulphate and distilled at 110° . (Found : S, 68.65. Calc. for $C_2H_6S_2$: S, 68.1 per cent). A solid distilled with water vapour into the condenser, which was scraped out and crystallised from alcohol and identified to be camphor, m.p. 178° (mixed m.p.).

S-Ethylcamphor, prepared by the same method as described in the case of S-methylcamphor, has b.p. $105^{\circ}/8$ mm. (Found : C, 73.31; H, 10.42; S, 16.48; M. W., 198. $C_{12}H_{20}S$ requires C, 73.47; H, 10.2; S, 16.33 per cent. M.W., 196). It has got a faint smell resembling that of sulphides, but on keeping for a few days it gives the smell of mercaptans. It decolourises cold, dilute solutions of bromine and acid permanganate. On hydrolysis with 10% sulphuric acid as described above, it gives ethylmercaptan characterised by its lead salt, m.p. 150° , and camphor, m.p. 178° . On heating with aniline or phenylhydrazine it gives ethylmercaptan which was identified by oxidising it to diethyl disulphide, b.p. 153° . (Found : S, 52.52. Calc. for $C_4H_{10}S_2$: S, 52.46 per cent).

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